

Microfinance Banking and Financial Inclusion in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of microfinance banking on financial inclusion in Nigeria from 2006 to 2021. The precise goals are to: examine the relationship between microfinance banks' interest rate and financial inclusion in Nigeria; examine if the number of microfinance bank branches affect financial inclusion in Nigeria in Nigeria. Financial inclusion as the dependent variable was measured using bank loans to rural regions and deposits from rural regions. While microfinance banking was measured with microfinance bank interest rate, number of microfinance bank branches, number of depositors with microfinance banks and microfinance bank assets. The error correction model was used in the empirical analysis. To ensure stationarity of variables, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is utilized. The reliability of the results is ensured by the Engle and Granger tests, which determine if the residuals of cointegration are stationary Findings showed that financial inclusion in Nigeria is positively impacted by microfinance banking. Particularly, bank loans to rural regions and deposits from rural regions are significantly impacted by microfinance banks' interest rates. The number of microfinance branches has a favourable impact on bank loans to rural regions, but a negative impact on deposits from rural regions.

Keywords: microfinance, Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF), financial, banking, inclusion.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria and throughout the world, microfinance banks are becoming a major means of finance for low-income households, small businesses, and those who do not have access to conventional financial services offered by commercial banks. A crucial factor in enhancing the socioeconomic situation of low-income business owners is microfinance banking (Murad & Idewe, 2017). It is widely recognized that by providing low-income individuals with access to a variety of financial

services including insurance, savings, overdraft, and financial literacy, microfinance may help eliminate poverty. Through its many financial services, microfinance banks have made it easy for the underprivileged to climb the financial ladder (Kama & Adigun, 2018). Microfinance banks have also been seen as one of the tools to fight financial exclusion, which is regarded to be a major cause of poverty, making microfinance banks a tool for fostering financial inclusion (Mbutor & Uba, 2019).

The basis of financial inclusion is attempting to ensure that a variety of relevant financial services are available to all income classes of individuals, as well as enabling them to understand and access such financial services (Ene & Inemesit, 2015). It involves paying special attention to segments of the population that have historically been excluded from the formal financial sector of the economy because of the level of their income, volatility, education, lack of information, gender, geographical location, and level of financial literacy (Demirgus-Kunt, 2018). Financial inclusion does not indicate that everybody will use all accessible financial services; rather, it implies that everyone has the opportunity to do so (Ene & Inemesit, 2015). All segment of the economy should have access to a range of financial services as they improve their standard of living. Microfinance banks are institution that provide accessibility of various financial service to everyone especially those who do not have access to financial services offered by commercial banks. Microfinance banks help to empower the poor and give valuable resources to aid in their economic development process. Hence the need to tap into the untapped potential of those individuals and businesses who are frequently excluded from or underserved by the formal financial sector, allowing them to engage in economic activities, build capacity, manage risk, and strengthen their human and physical capital (Ene & Inemesit, 2015).

In Nigeria, the role of microfinance banking in encouraging financial inclusion is very crucial. The concept of Microfinance bank is not new in Nigeria; it has existed for a long time in the shape of esusu, a rotating contributory savings program popular among market vendors. Nigerians have long attempted to meet their financial needs using informal microfinance approaches (Okpara, 2010). However, as the economy has become more sophisticated, the limitations of this method have become clear. This is a key factor in the introduction of the microfinance policy in 2005, a movement that paved way for the introduction of microfinance banking in Nigeria to address this acknowledged shortcoming in the informal microfinance industry. Based on the primary goal of microfinance banks and its anticipated primary area of operation, microfinance banks (MFBs) have been given a crucial position in the national financial inclusion plan in Nigeria. Since it is widely accepted that microfinance banks provide financial services to low-income households who have no access to formal financial services, it is anticipated that they will operate primarily in rural and semi-urban areas, and it has also been established that the majority of those who are financially excluded are low-income and most of them live in rural areas. (Aurora 2019; Ifionu, & Ibe 2019). It is against this background that this study investigates the impact of microfinance banking on financial inclusion in Nigeria

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

Nigeria is a country that is facing a unique struggle with financial inclusion, financial inclusion has been a major concern of the Nigerian government, also the cashless policy which the Nigerian government is clamouring on depends hugely on financial inclusion. Despite efforts to increase

financial inclusion, Nigeria has not experienced much of an improvement in financial inclusion, which is one of the main reasons that this topic has been and is still so widely discussed. The massive financial access gap in Nigeria and the difficulties with financial inclusion need the construction of a suitable/conducive environment for the private sector and other stakeholders to perform their respective roles. This is a key factor in the introduction of the Microfinance Policy in December 2005, a move that paved the way for the development of microfinance banking in Nigeria (Sanusi, 2010).

Today there are over 916 licenced microfinance banks in Nigeria, financial inclusion is influenced by some microfinance banking factors which include microfinance bank's interest, the number of microfinance bank branches, the number of depositors with microfinance banks, and microfinance bank assets. One major problem impeding the development of microfinance banks is the lack of a banking culture in rural areas and among the poor. These people typically borrow money from friends and family and repay it in full, regardless of how long the loans are outstanding. As a result, they have trouble comprehending how interest on bank loans is paid.

Due to the historical exclusion of some people from the official financial sector due to factors like their income level and volatility, gender, geography, kind of activity, or degree of financial knowledge, certain segments of the population need to get special attention (Demirguc-Kunt, 2018). In doing so, it is necessary to unlock the unrealized potential of those people and organizations that are frequently left out of or underserved by the formal financial system and to give them the tools they need to build their capacities, strengthen their human and material capital, participate in income-generating activities, and manage the risks related to their livelihoods. Although everyone has the choice to utilize them, financial inclusion does not mean that they will all use the financial services that are offered. Individuals must have access to a range of financial services as their level of living rises (The World Bank, 2015).

Studies carried out in Nigeria have not discussed extensively the microfinance banking and financial inclusion. Previous research concentrated on how financial inclusion either affects microfinance banks or microfinance bank affects financial inclusion and other variables like economic growth, poverty, and women (Ozili, 2020; Nkwede, 2015; Babajide, Adegboye, & Omankhanlem, 2015; Mbutor & Uba, 2013; Aduda & Kalunda, 2012; Demirguc-Kunt, Thorsten & Patrick, 2008) amongst others. Despite the significant value and growth potential, none of the few studies examined microfinance banking and financial inclusion combining microfinance banks' interest, the number of microfinance bank branches, the number of depositors with microfinance banks and microfinance bank assets as the independent variables in Nigeria. Due to their minimal use in previous studies these variables were taken into consideration for this study. Moreover, concerning the data analysis methods, it has been noticed that most of the empirical studies have used Structural equation modeling (SEM) through analysis of moment structures (AMOS), fully modified ordinary least square, and Partial Least Square (PLS). as (Aigbovo & Akunoma, 2017; Adeola & Evans, 2017; Hussaini & Chibuzo, 2018; Bongomin, Ntayi, & Malinga, 2020). Consequently, this study will fill the identified gap by empirically examining microfinance banking and financial inclusion using the combination of microfinance banks' interest, the number of microfinance bank branches, the number of depositors with microfinance

banks and microfinance bank assets as the independent variables as well as use the ordinary least square (ECM) analytical approach.

1.3 Research Questions

In light of this, the study provides answer to the following questions:

1. What is the relationship between microfinance banks interest rate and financial inclusion in Nigeria?
2. What is the impact of the number of microfinance bank branches on financial inclusion in Nigeria?
3. How does number of depositors with microfinance banks affect financial inclusion in Nigeria?
4. What effect does Microfinance bank assets have on financial inclusion in Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to investigate the effects of microfinance banking on financial inclusion in Nigeria. The precise goals are to:

1. examine the relationship between microfinance banks' interest rate and financial inclusion in Nigeria;
2. investigate if the number of microfinance bank branches affect financial inclusion in Nigeria and on financial inclusion in Nigeria;
3. ascertain whether the number of depositors with microfinance banks affect financial inclusion in Nigeria; and to
4. determine the impact Microfinance bank assets have on financial inclusion in Nigeria.

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

To address the above research objectives, the following research hypotheses are stated in their null forms as follows:

H₀₁. Microfinance bank's interest has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

H₀₂. Number of microfinance bank branches has no significant effect on financial inclusion in Nigeria

H₀₃. Number of depositors with microfinance banks has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

H₀₄. Microfinance bank credits has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

1.6 Scope of the Study

This scope of this study is financial inclusion and microfinance in Nigeria. The geographical scope consists of microfinance banks in Nigeria. The study covers a 15-year period, ranging from 2006 to 2021. This period was specifically selected because microfinance banking was introduced during this period, hence a study carried out within this period will provide valuable information as to the extent to which microfinance banking impact financial inclusion in Nigeria. All licenced microfinance banks make up the sample size of the study as a result aggregate data of all microfinance banks as reported by CBN statistical bulletin was used for this study. The justification for this sample size is to have a robust analysis of the relationship between microfinance banking and financial inclusion in Nigeria.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial as an extension of knowledge to the existing body of literature on the topic microfinance banking and financial inclusion in Nigeria. The study in addition will be of benefits to researchers, microfinance bank executives, policy makers and regulators.

For management, this research is of great importance to microfinance bank as it provides policy recommendations on how and what decisions should be taken to run the operations of the bank.

The results of this study will be beneficial to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other financial authorities in ensuring that policies are geared in directions that could be more effective in achieving financial inclusion through microfinance banks.

Finally, in an effort to increase human understanding, this work will be important to scholars in areas connected to finance, accounting, and management.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the longitudinal research design. This research design was used because it allows the study to follow changes in behavior, attitudes, or beliefs over a period of years or decades. In addition to capturing changes that a cross-sectional study would have missed, longitudinal research design may be conducted over a long period of time, allowing for a more thorough knowledge of population changes.

The error correction model is used since the study is a longitudinal study. Its use is justified by the fact that it is a time series regression model that produces equilibrium for both long- and short-term time series. It serves as a stochastic trend of the effect of one-point series variable on another and essentially demonstrates how the dependent variable returns to equilibrium when other variables are altered. Data acquired from CBN statistical bulletin were evaluated using the econometric program Stata 15. It is crucial to demonstrate that time series data is susceptible to inaccuracies because of changes in bank loans and deposits, hence several tests have been conducted to take account of these shortcomings.

To determine if the variables under investigation are stationary, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is utilized. The reliability of the results is ensured by the Engle and Granger tests, which determine if the residuals of cointegration are stationary. The presence of multicollinearity was

assessed using the variance inflation factor. Calculating this percentage for each independent variable enables us to ensure that the model is well-defined and functional.

Population and Sample size of the study

The source of data for the study are secondary sources including data from CBN statistical bulletin (2021) and Nigerian bureau of statistics. This entailed using microfinance banks for fifteen (15) years ranging from 2006-2021.

Model Specification

The model adopted for this study is derived from previous study carried out by Aigbovo and Akunoma (2020). The functional form of their model is stated thus:

$$PIDEX = (CBBR, BCB, NATM, MBFL) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (1)$$

The econometric form of the model is stated as:

$$PIDEX_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CBBR_t + \beta_2 BCB_t + \beta_3 NATM_t + \beta_4 MBFL_t + \epsilon_t \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where:

PIDEX = Poverty Index

CBBR = Bank branches

BCB = Borrower of banks

NATM = Numbers of ATM

MFBL = Microfinance bank loan

ϵ : error term

with slight modification to the work of Aigbovo and Akunoma, (2020) the specification of two models is prompted by the fact that the study's dependent variable will be represented by two metrics, such as deposits from and loans to rural areas. The two models stated in their functional form are given below:

$$BI = (MICBI, MINUB, DEP, MICRA) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (3)$$

$$DE = (MICBI, MINUB, DEP, MICRA) \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (4)$$

The models above expressed in their econometric form is given below:

$$BI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MICBI_t + \beta_2 MINUB_t + \beta_3 DEP_t + \beta_4 MICRA_t + \epsilon_t \dots \dots \dots 5$$

$$DE_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MICBI_t + \beta_2 MINUB_t + \beta_3 DEP_t + \beta_4 MICRA_t + \epsilon_t \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Where;

Stats	BI	DE	MICBI	MINUB	DEP	MICRA
Mean	129617.1	126162.3	23.6725	797.1875	27.05563	15436.31
Std. Dev.	86962.12	67195.79	11.36768	129.081	15.88631	5844.908
Mean	129617.1	126162.3	23.6725	797.1875	27.05563	15436.31
Skewness	.1867431	.3263355	.4282835	-.5296404	-.3538512	.2756053
Kurtosis	1.478647	2.040919	2.280299	2.448244	1.664515	2.617881
N	16	16	16	16	16	16

BI = bank loans to rural area

DE: Deposit from rural area

MICBI: Microfinance bank interest rate

MINUB: Number of branches

DEP: Number of depositors

MICRE: Microfinance asset

e: error term.

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 31: Descriptive Statistics

The table displays the results of descriptive statistics used to determine the measure of central tendency as well as the measure of dispersion of the variables in the research. The mean of bank loans to rural regions is 129617.1, with a standard deviation of 86962.12, showing that the variable is well dispersed and loans to rural areas are widely spread, according to the results in table 4.1. The mean of deposits from rural areas is 126162.3 with a standard deviation of 67195.79 meaning the variables is well spread also in terms of receiving deposits from rural areas. The average microfinance bank interest rate is 23.7, indicating that the interest rate offered by microfinance banks is 24% on average. The standard deviation of the variable is 11.4, suggesting a modest

amount of dispersion. The mean number of microfinance bank branches is 797.67, suggesting that the country's average number of microfinance bank branches is 797, with a standard deviation of 129, showing a wide variety of branches. The mean of number of depositors is 27.08, which means that a microfinance bank on the average has 27.08 depositors at a particular point in time. The standard deviation of 15.9 indicate that the number of depositors is moderately spread. The variable, microfinance assets, has a mean value of 15436.31 and a standard deviation of 5844.908, showing that it is widely distributed.

Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the distribution of a random variable around its mean. It is used to determine how far something deviates from the norm. Positive skewness refers to a distribution with an asymmetric tail that extends toward greater positive values. A distribution with negative skewness has an asymmetric tail that extends toward bigger negative values. A statistic called kurtosis may be used to assess whether the distribution of a random variable is peaked or flat around its mean. The degree to which the observations are closely grouped around the mean is measured. Whereas a distribution with a low kurtosis is typically flat and has fewer outliers, one with a high kurtosis is peaked and has a lot of them.

The type of data will determine the suitable skewness and kurtosis levels. Kurtosis and skewness should both be three for data that is considered to be normal. There is no particular set of values that may be used to define normalcy for non-normal data. Although it is generally acknowledged that kurtosis values between -2 and 8 and skewness values between -2 and 2 are within the usual range (1). (Khandelwal & Khandelwal 2017). The variables in this study pass the test for normalcy since their skewness and kurtosis values are all within the benchmark.

Table 3.2: Linearity of Variables

	BI	DE	MICBI	MINUB	DEP	MICRA
BI	1.0000					
DE	0.9700	1.0000				
MICBI	0.3739	0.4090	1.0000			
MINUB	-0.0005	-0.1708	-0.3832	1.0000		
DEP	0.7305	0.7316	0.0500	0.1455	1.0000	
MICRA	0.8774	0.8638	0.2397	0.0227	0.4650	1.0000

Table 3.2 presents the results of the correlation investigation. The correlation coefficient demonstrated that the regressand and the regressors had a linear connection. As a consequence, the variable's coefficient of correlation with itself was (1.00), indicating a perfect connection. The table demonstrates that there is a positive association between all factors and bank loans to rural regions, with the exception of microfinance bank branches (negative correlation). When the numbers for deposits into rural regions were compared, it was discovered that every variable, with the exception of microfinance bank branches, had a positive link with deposits into rural areas. It was noted that the positive correlation for the variables (microfinance assets, number of depositors), was substantial and even over the advised level of 0.7. (Stundenmund, 2014). This finding raised the possibility that the model could have multicollinearity issues. The variance inflation factor test was used to check for any multicollinearity issues in the model and the variables being investigated.

Table 3.3: Multicollinearity test

Equation 3: Dependent Variable-Bank loans to rural Areas

VARIABLE	VIF	1/VIF
INTERCEPT	68.23	0.014656
MINUB	50.60	0.019764
MICRA	11.48	0.087080
MICBI	7.11	0.140667
DEP	5.35	0.186984

Source: (Authors Computation using Stata 15)

Centered VIF= VIF

Uncentered VIF= 1/VIF

The Multicollinearity test result is shown in Table 3.3. The findings show that, with the exception of microfinance assets, all variables' centered VIF were below 10, as suggested by (Stundenmund, 2014). This suggests that there were no Multicollinearity issues with the study's variables or model. The outcome of the above-discussed linearity of variables is further confirmed and strengthened by this conclusion.

Table 3.4: Equation 4 Multicollinearity test

Dependent Variable: Deposit from rural areas

VARIABLE	VIF	1/VIF
INTERCEPT	68.23	0.014656
MINUB	50.60	0.019764
MICRA	11.48	0.087080
MICBI	7.11	0.140667
DEP	5.35	0.186984

Source: (Authors Computation using Stata 15)

Centered VIF= VIF

Uncentered VIF= 1/VIF

The Multicollinearity test result is shown in Table 3.4. The findings show that, with the exception of microfinance assets, all variables' centered VIF were below 10, as suggested by (Studenmund, 2014). This suggests that there were no Multicollinearity issues with the study's variables or model. The outcome of the above-discussed linearity of variables is further confirmed and strengthened by this conclusion.

Table 3.5: Constant residual error test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
chi2(4) = 5.81
Prob > chi2 = 0.2139

Source: Authors Computation 2023

Table 3.5 displays the results of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for the constant residual error of heteroskedasticity. $F(4) = 0.2139$, $p > .05$. The study's results revealed that the model is not heteroskedastic.

Table 3.6: Ramsey Retest

$F(3, 8) = 2.50$
Prob > F = 0.1333

Model Specification was tested using the Ramsey RESET Test. $F(3, 8) = 0.1333, p > .05$. The analysis's findings demonstrated that there was no model misspecification. This indicates that the model for the study was correctly defined and that no variables were omitted (Studenmund, 2014).

3.4 Unit Root Test

Table 3.7: Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test @ levels and at first difference

Unit root tests at levels				
Variables	ADF-Test Statistic	95% Critical ADF Value	Prob	Remarks
BI	-0.423	-3.0000	0.3958	Non-stationary
De	-3.595026	-0.774372	0.9554	Non-stationary
MICBI	-4.181564	-3.759743	0.0249	Stationary
MINUB	-3.241949	-3.574244	0.0963	Non-stationary
DEP	-3.854345	-3.612199	0.0309	Stationary
MICRA	-2.851418	-1.968430	0.0079	Stationary
Unit root test at 1st difference				
Variables	ADF-Test Statistic	95% Critical ADF Value	Prob	Remarks
BI	-4.496584	-3.587527	0.0070	Stationary
De	-7.797070	-3.595026	0.0000	Stationary
MICBI	-4.919295	-3.791172	0.0083	Stationary
MINUB	-7.896181	-3.580622	0.0000	Stationary
DEP	-5.745363	-3.622033	0.0006	Stationary

Source: (Authors Computation using Stata 15)

Table 3.7 displays the outcomes of the stationarity test using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. If you look at the table above It was observed that the majority of variables, including BI, DE, and MINUB, were non-stationary at rates but stationary at the first difference. Therefore, to imply that there is a long-term relationship between the estimated parameters. The error term (ECM) was also

shown to be stationary at the margin, highlighting the need of taking into account long-term correlations between variables (Sudenmund, 2014).

3.5 Multivariate Analysis

Table 3.8: Ordinary least squares (Error Correction Model)

Dependent Variable: BI

		R-Squared =	0.9406
		Prob > F	0.0000
		Adj. R-squared =	0.9190
	Coef.	T	p>[t]
MICBI	1541.827	2.44	0.033
MINUB	.1659396	0.00	0.998
DEP	2338.531	5.09	0.000
MICRA	9.380459	7.36	0.046

Source: (Authors Computation using Stata 15)

The model results from Table 3.8 provided estimates of the impact of microfinance banking on financial inclusion as determined by bank loans to rural regions. The F-statistic, which was 43.56 (p-value = 0.0000), is significant at 5%, indicating that the hypothesis that the dependent and independent variables have a significant linear connection cannot be disproved. The model's R2 is 94%, while its corrected R2 is 91%. According to the regression estimate's adjusted R2 of 91%, the independent variables in the model account for about 91% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable, and the remaining 9% is accounted for by variables that were not included in the model but were effectively captured by the standard error of the regression.

According to the findings, bank loans to rural regions are positively and significantly impacted by microfinance bank interest rates. At a 95% confidence level, it was discovered that the variable number of microfinance branches had a favorable and non-significant impact on bank loans to rural regions. Bank loans to rural regions were shown to benefit from the changing number of depositors, and this impact was judged to be significant at a 95% confidence level. Microfinance assets were shown to boost bank loans to rural areas; this effect was found to be statistically significant at the 95% confidence level.

Table 3.9: Ordinary least squares (Error Correction Model)

Dependent Variable: DE

		R-Squared =	0.9698
		Prob > F	0.0000
		Adj. R-squared =	0.9588
	Coef.	t	p>[t]
MICBI	986.8802	348.3561	0.016
MINUB	-98.18142	30.06738	0.008
DEP	1973.461	253.4478	0.000
MICRA	7.02607	.7030336	0.000

Source: (Authors Computation using Stata 15)

The model results from Table 3.9 provided estimates of the impact of microfinance banking on financial inclusion as determined by bank loans to rural regions. The F-statistic of 88.21 (p-value = 0.0000) is significant at 5%, indicating that the hypothesis that the dependent and independent variables have a significant linear connection cannot be disproved. The R-Square of the model is 97%, whereas the R-Square after correction is 96%. According to the regression estimate's adjusted R2 of 96%, the independent variables in the model account for about 96% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable, while the remaining 4% is accounted for by variables that were not included in the model but were effectively captured by the standard error of the regression.

According to the findings, rural deposits have a favorable and considerable impact on the interest rate of microfinance banks. At a 95% confidence level, it was discovered that the varying number of microfinance branches had a detrimental and substantial impact on deposits from rural regions. Deposits from rural locations were found to benefit from the changing number of depositors, and this impact was determined to be significant at a 95% confidence level. Deposits from rural regions were shown to benefit from microfinance assets; this impact was judged to be statistically significant at the 95% confidence level.

3.6 Testing of Hypotheses

To decide the course of the study, it is necessary to experimentally test the hypotheses that were put out. Thus, they are examined in the following ways.

Hypothesis 1

H₀: Microfinance bank's interest rate has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

Significance Level: 5%

Rejection region: If the probability value is smaller than the calculated P-value, accept the null hypothesis; otherwise Accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

With p-values of 0.033 (BI) and 0.016 (DE), respectively, and falling within the rejection region, the regression results in tables 4.8 and 4.9 demonstrate that microfinance bank interest rates were found to have a positive and significant effect on financial inclusion. As a result, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: Number of microfinance bank branches has no significant effect on financial inclusion in Nigeria

Significance Level: 5% Rejection region: If the probability value is smaller than the calculated P-value, accept the null hypothesis; otherwise Accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis. According to the model results in tables 4.8 and 4.9, the number of microfinance branches had a positive but minor influence on bank loans (0.998) and a negative but substantial effect on deposits from rural regions (0.008). As a result, the null hypothesis is accepted because this does not lie inside the rejection zone.

Hypothesis 3

H₀: Number of depositors with microfinance banks has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

Significance Level: 5%

Rejection region: If the probability value is smaller than the calculated P-value, accept the null hypothesis; otherwise Accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

Looking at the regression results in tables 4.8 and 4.9 reveals that bank loans to (0.00) and deposits from (0.00) rural regions were shown to be positively and significantly impacted by the number of depositors. As a result, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted because this does fall inside the rejection zone.

Hypothesis 4

H₀: Microfinance bank assets has no significant impact on financial inclusion in Nigeria

Significance Level: 5%

Rejection region: If the probability value is smaller than the calculated P-value, accept the null hypothesis; otherwise Accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

The regression results in tables 4.8 and 4.9 demonstrate that microfinance bank assets were found to have a positive and significant impact on financial inclusion (bank loan to rural areas-0.00, deposit from rural areas-0.00). As these values fall within the rejection region, the null hypothesis will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted

4.0 CONCLUSION

The study looked at how Nigerian financial inclusion has been affected by microfinance banking. This was nevertheless accomplished through the specific goals, which included determining the impact of the interest rate charged by microfinance banks on bank loans to and deposits from rural areas, examining the impact of the number of microfinance branches on bank loans to and deposits from rural areas, identifying the impact of the number of depositors on bank loans to and deposits from rural areas, and determining the impact of microfinance assets.

The inferential statistic's findings showed that:

Microfinance bank interest rate has a positive and significant effect on bank loans to rural areas and deposits from rural areas;

Number of microfinance branches has a positive effect on bank loans to rural areas but a negative effect on deposits from rural areas.

Number of depositors was discovered to have a favourable and considerable impact on bank loans to rural areas and deposits from rural regions.

Microfinance bank asset has a favourable and considerable impact on bank loans to rural areas and deposits from rural regions,

In conclusion, financial inclusion and microfinance have the potential to be effective tools for Nigerian economic growth, but there are still a number of issues that must be resolved before this can happen. It is crucial to make sure that the right laws are in place to safeguard consumers and that credit is more easily accessible. In order to facilitate access to financial services, it is also necessary to upgrade the banking infrastructure in rural regions. In order for more individuals to benefit from the possibilities of microfinance banking and financial inclusion, it is crucial to keep promoting financial literacy and awareness.

Recommendations

The success of microfinance banking and financial inclusion in Nigeria depends on the ongoing promotion of financial literacy and awareness as well as the development of regulatory frameworks that are supportive of the expansion of these services.

- The interest rate charged by microfinance banks should be well monitored and regulated by the authorities to prevent excess rates being charged.
- There has to be regulation in the number of microfinance bank branches since this might have an adverse effect on financial inclusion in the nation.
- It is important to promote the use of microfinance banks by depositors, especially in rural regions, since this would increase the amount of money available for development in those areas.
- Microfinance banks should endeavour to increase the size of its assets as it will have a favourable impact on financial inclusion activities in the country.
- It's also crucial to make sure that rules are in place to safeguard consumers and that loan access is made more cheap. In order to increase the number of individuals who have access to financial services, it is crucial to upgrade the banking infrastructure in rural regions. Microfinance banking and financial inclusion may be a powerful instrument for economic growth in Nigeria with the correct policies in place.

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